

1 Complexity of graphite formation in response to metamorphic
2 methane generation and transformation in an orogenic ultramafic
3 body

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23

24 Abstract

25 The fate of carbon in subduction is explored by considering fluid-rock interactions in a
26 body of metamorphosed ultramafic rocks from the Appalachian belt as potential
27 proxies for metasomatism and carbon recycling (e.g., infiltration, solution,
28 precipitation) in the mantle wedge at convergent margins. Ultramafic rocks may record
29 intense redox variations affecting the exchanges between solid and fluid carbon-
30 bearing phases. The Belvidere Mountain Complex (BMC) in Vermont, USA is an
31 ultramafic body that underwent Ordovician Taconic subduction metamorphism up to
32 510-520 °C and 0.9-1.3 GPa. Previous investigations indicate that the BMC
33 experienced partial serpentinization and carbon recycling in the subduction zone. Here
34 bulk $\delta^{11}\text{B}$, $\text{Sr}^{87}/\text{Sr}^{86}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, data, in-situ microRaman spectroscopy and bulk $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$
35 and $\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{CH}_4}$ on fluid inclusions, and numerical modeling results aim to constrain the
36 origin and formation mechanisms of carbon-bearing solid and fluid phases in the BMC.
37 Bulk $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios and $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ of the BMC rocks suggest infiltration of metasediment-
38 derived fluids inside the mafic/ultramafic body. Carbonates present in the studied
39 ultramafic and mafic rocks have $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values ranging from -7.26 to -1.27‰. This range
40 was found to record progressive reduction of an initial isotopically light carbonate to
41 methane under reducing conditions. MicroRaman spectroscopy on fluid inclusions
42 confirms CH_4 -rich gaseous compositions, along with N_2 , NH_3 , and S-H compounds,
43 which support a metasedimentary origin for the fluid infiltrating the BMC. Methane-rich

44 fluid inclusions were observed in partially serpentinized peridotites, in carbonate veins,
45 and in amphibolite bodies associated with the ultramafic body, and as well in the
46 surrounding metasedimentary rock units. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ of methane in fluid
47 inclusions show a wide range of values in ultramafic rocks from -45.2‰ to -12.6‰ for
48 carbon and -226‰ to -140‰ for hydrogen. The methane stable isotope data suggest
49 the presence of two types of methane preserved in studied samples, formed by high-
50 temperature thermogenic processes of metamorphosed graphitic carbon and by
51 abiotic conversion of more oxidized carbon bearing species in the presence of H_2 -rich
52 fluids produced during metamorphic serpentinization. The BMC also hosts a
53 remarkable example of graphite deposit, with up to 3.90 wt% graphite, along a ~6 m-
54 thick zone within the serpentinized ultramafic body and along lithologic contacts. The
55 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ composition of the graphite clusters at -15‰ (VPBD), which is consistent with the
56 composition of graphite precipitating from the mixing of the two types of methane-
57 bearing fluids identified in fluid inclusions. The mixing between metasediment-derived
58 and serpentinization-related methane-rich fluids is proposed as the mechanism
59 leading to graphite precipitation. Further complexity is suggested by carbonate
60 reduction evidenced in the samples, which may have locally contributed to the
61 formation of graphite on the precursor carbonate domains. The BMC rocks highlight
62 the variability of carbon recycling processes, including carbon mobilization from
63 multiple solid sources, and mixing of multiple carbon-bearing fluids in a dynamic fluid-
64 rock system, with carbon mobilization and sink adapting to evolving redox conditions.

65

66 Keywords: Abiotic methane; C fluxes at subductions zones; Natural graphite; Isotopes;
67 Belvidere Mountain Complex

69 1 Introduction

70 Subduction is a major actor in the cycling of carbon between surface and deep
71 reservoirs. As material is brought down along the subducted slab, fluid release and
72 interaction with the overlying mantle wedge creates complex pathways for element
73 mobility as well as fluid intake and outtake (Dasgupta, 2013; Dasgupta and
74 Hirschmann, 2010; Manning, 2014). Metamorphic reactions along the subduction path
75 can regulate element mobility as well as fluid speciation (e.g, Evans, 2012; Hayes and
76 Waldbauer, 2006). Carbon in subduction zone rocks can be present under different
77 valence states, from -4 to +4, in various forms, such as carbonate, organic matter, and
78 several fluid species such as CO₂, CH₄, as well as many others (e.g. Manning et al.,
79 2013; Sverjensky et al., 2020). Carbon mobilization in subduction zones is known to
80 produce different carbonic fluids: CO₂-rich fluids resulting from decarbonation
81 reactions (Gorman et al., 2006; Kerrick and Connolly, 1998, 2001a, 2001b; Stewart et
82 al., 2019), carbonate dissolution (e.g., Ague and Nicolescu, 2014; Facq et al., 2014;
83 Frezzotti et al., 2011; Piccoli et al., 2021), CH₄-rich fluids from serpentinization of
84 preserved peridotite in the slab and of the overlying mantle wedge (Boutier et al., 2021;
85 Peng et al., 2021; Vitale Brovarone et al., 2020a, 2017) or from organic matter-rich
86 metasedimentary rocks (Clift, 2017; Tumiati et al., 2020; Vitale Brovarone et al.,
87 2020b) and mantle derived CO₂/CH₄ fluids (Dasgupta, 2013 and references therein;
88 Green et al., 1987). The precipitation of carbon-bearing minerals, most notably
89 carbonates, graphite, and diamond, as well as other compounds is largely related to
90 the transformation of these fluids during the percolation through crustal and mantle
91 rocks. The interplay and interrelations among processes of carbon mobilization and
92 precipitation –hereafter carbon recycling– at subduction zones are central in the

93 evolution of Earth and life, and also to assess the potential habitability of other celestial
94 bodies where subduction is or was once active (Giovannelli et al., 2022). The formation
95 and migration of CH₄ and associated reduced fluid species –most notably H₂– is of
96 particular interest in the study of how life emerged on Earth and potentially elsewhere,
97 and how deep it could extend in the subsurface biosphere (Colman et al., 2017; Gold,
98 1992; Ménez et al., 2018; Plümpner et al., 2017; Schrenk et al., 2013).

99 The fate of metamorphic methane in subduction is strongly dependent upon multiple
100 fluid-rock interactions that may take place in slab and mantle wedge forming rocks.
101 For instance, prograde metamorphism of organic-rich metapelitic rocks may release
102 aqueous fluids rich in CH₄, migration of which may favor the reactivity of more oxidized
103 carbonate-rich rocks and the precipitation of graphite along lithologic boundaries
104 (Evans et al., 2002). Or, reducing fluids derived from ultramafic or mafic rocks may
105 lead to the reduction of carbonate minerals, the formation of abiotic methane, and/or
106 the precipitation of graphite (Galvez et al., 2013; Tao et al., 2018; Vitale Brovarone et
107 al., 2017). Ultimately, the migration of metamorphic methane may support metabolic
108 reactions in the deep subsurface biosphere (Vitale Brovarone et al., 2020a). However,
109 field examples recording interaction of reduced carbon-rich fluids remain insufficient
110 to understand the fate of metamorphic methane at depth. Here we present results from
111 the Belvidere Mountain complex (BMC). The BMC consists of an ultramafic/mafic body
112 that has been interpreted as a fragment of the Iapetus ocean that was involved in the
113 Taconic orogeny and that recorded HP metamorphism during the Ordovician (Chew
114 and van Staal, 2014; Gale, 1980; Honsberger et al., 2017). This locality hosts a
115 remarkable example of metamorphic methane formation and migration and fluid-
116 mediated graphite deposition in a subduction zone. This work integrates field,
117 microstructural, fluid inclusion, major and trace element and isotopic geochemical data

118 to investigate the mechanisms of metamorphic methane formation, migration, and
119 transformation in a subduction setting.

120 2 Geologic settings

121 The Belvidere Mountain Complex (BMC) is a body of mafic/ultramafic rocks located in
122 Northern Vermont and belonging to the Appalachian Mountain system. The complex
123 has been interpreted as a remnant of an ocean-continent transition zone associated
124 with the extension of the Laurentian margin that underwent peak blueschist-facies
125 metamorphism during the Ordovician Taconic subduction (Chew and van Staal, 2014;
126 Gale, 1980). It exhibits variably serpentinized peridotites, mainly dunite and
127 harzburgite, associated with metabasic and metafelsic rocks. The BMC is tectonically
128 embedded within Proterozoic to Cambrian metasedimentary and metavolcanic
129 formations (Fig. 1). Taconic age, peak blueschist-facies metamorphic conditions of the
130 BMC are constrained at 0.9-1.3 GPa and 510-520 °C in metabasic rocks (Honsberger
131 et al., 2017; Laird et al., 1993). A recent study provides additional insight on the PT
132 path of the massif with evidence of mineral assemblages stable at ~1.65–2.0 GPa and
133 ~450–480 °C, and ~1.0–1.4 GPa and ~515–550 °C (Honsberger, 2023). The rocks
134 preserve features of interactions with aqueous fluids and in the subduction zone,
135 leading to variable serpentinization (10-100 vol% serpentine) (Boutier et al., 2021;
136 Labotka and Albee, 1979). This tectonometamorphic event was dated at 505-473 Ma
137 by $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ amphibole and mica geochronology (Castonguay et al., 2012; Laird et al.,
138 1993).

139

140 3 Methods

141 MicroRaman spectroscopy of minerals and fluid inclusions was performed at the
142 Department of Earth Sciences, University of Turin, with a LabRAM HR (VIS) (HORIBA
143 Jobin Yvon) equipped with a 532.11 nm, solid-state Nd laser, a Super Notch Plus filter
144 with a grating of 600 grooves/mm leading to a spectral resolution of 1 cm^{-1} . The laser
145 emission power was set at 80 mW and focused to $5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ with a 100x objective with a
146 laser power on the sample $< 5\text{ mW}$. Calibration was performed using the 520.6 cm^{-1}
147 band of a silicon standard for the $100\text{-}2000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range, and the 2331 cm^{-1} band of
148 atmospheric N_2 for the $2000\text{-}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range. Four accumulations of 30–60 s were
149 collected for each spectrum. Raman spectra of fluid inclusions were performed on
150 double-polished thick sections.

151 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) imaging and energy-dispersive X-ray
152 spectroscopy (EDS) compositional analyses were carried out using a Zeiss EVO15
153 equipped with a LaB6 source, a high-definition backscattered electron detector
154 (HDBSE), and an Oxford Instruments UltimMax 100 detector at the Deep Carbon Lab,
155 (Department of Biological, Geological, and Environmental Sciences, University of
156 Bologna). Additional analyses were performed with a tungsten (W) SEM-JEOL JSM-
157 IT300LV Scanning Electron Microscope combined with an energy dispersive
158 spectrometry (EDS) Energy 200 system and an SDD X-Act3 detector (Oxford Inca
159 Energy) at the Department of Earth Sciences of Turin University. Data were processed
160 with the AztecLive and INCA softwares from Oxford Instruments. Semi-quantitative
161 analysis employed 15kV accelerating voltage and a beam current of 50 nA and 20 s
162 to 40 s counting total time. Natural and synthetic mineral and oxide standards were
163 employed. EDS calibration was made using Cobalt standard.

164 Quantitative wavelength-dispersive spectrometer (WDS) analyses were carried out
165 using a JEOL 8200 Super Probe with a W source at the Department of Earth Sciences
166 “Ardito Desio” of Milan University. The microprobe operating settings under maximum
167 emission peak were 15kV accelerating voltage under 5 nA, beam diameter 1 μm ,
168 counting time 30 s, and background counting time 10 s. Sixteen oxide compositions
169 were measured, using synthetic and natural standards: grossular (Si, Al and Ca),
170 omphacite (Na), K-feldspar (K), fayalite (Fe), forsterite (Mg), rhodonite (Mn), niccolite
171 (Ni), ilmenite (Ti), galena (Pb and S), pure Cr, pure Zn and pure Cu.

172 Portions of samples were cut to remove weathered and surface organic contamination,
173 and then crushed and pulverized with Plattner’s steel and agate mortars. Considering
174 the very high amount of graphite, the potential effect of organic contaminations by
175 groundwater circulation was considered negligible. Analyses of total organic carbon
176 (TOC) were performed on aliquots of about 1 g of dried, decarbonated samples (HCl,
177 6 mol/L, attacked at ambient temperature for one night) using a Flash EA1112
178 elemental analyzer coupled to a Thermo Finnigan DELTA plus XP isotope ratio mass
179 spectrometer via a ConFlo IV interface at IPGP, Paris. Aliquots of the companion, non-
180 decarbonated sample were also analyzed for Total Inorganic Carbon (TIC)+ Total
181 inorganic carbon (TOC). Graphitic C concentrations in samples presented herein
182 correspond to the TOC.

183 The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of carbonate were obtained at the Institute of Geosciences and
184 Earth Resources, Pisa, on a GasBench II with a continuous-flow IRMS setup, after the
185 method of Breitenbach and Bernasconi, (2011). Isotope ratios are reported in permil
186 (‰) using the conventional δ -notation and with respect to the Vienna Stanard Mean

187 Ocean Water (V-SMOW) for oxygen and Vienna Pee Dee Belemnite (V-PDB) for
188 carbon. Standard deviation was 0.05‰ for both $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$.

189 The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ of CH_4 was obtained at IFP energies nouvelles by extracting the
190 gas by crushing inclusion-rich samples in a sealed modified planetary mill. The
191 samples were placed in a ZrO jar and sealed by an inlet/outlet-equipped cover. The
192 jar was flushed with N_2 for around 60 seconds, then sealed and crushed at 700 rpm
193 for 240 seconds. The gas was then extracted from the jar by connecting vacuum
194 Exetainer[®] sample vials. Three vials were collected for each sample. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of each
195 sample was measured by two independent techniques: the first vial of each sample
196 was injected in triplicate in a Picarro G2210-i Isotope Analyzer, to obtain the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of
197 CH_4 and the C1/C2 ratio. The two other vials were used to analyze $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of
198 CH_4 with a GC-MS, respectively. Analyses by GC-MS were calibrated using two
199 internal gas standards.

200 Bulk $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ was analyzed at IGG-CNR, Pisa; for each sample ~0.2 g of sample powder
201 was treated by alkaline fusion in platinum crucibles with a 4:1 flux to sample ratio.
202 Boron was then extracted from the fusion cakes by repeated crushing and centrifuging
203 of the cakes in high pH B-free water. It was further purified by passing the solution
204 through anion and cation exchange columns. Anion columns were packed with
205 Amberlite IRA-743 boron-specific anion exchange resin, while cation-exchange
206 columns were packed with AG 50W-X8 resin. The procedure used an anion column
207 step, followed by a cation column step and then a final (repeat) anion column step to
208 produce the final purified boron solution, as described by (Agostini et al., 2021). Boron
209 isotopic compositions were measured on a Thermo Scientific[™] Neptune series multi-
210 collector (MC)-ICP-MS in Pisa, specially tuned for $^{11}\text{B}/^{10}\text{B}$ analysis, following Foster,
211 (2008). Samples were diluted to contain ~20 ppb B and were then bracketed with NBS

212 951 boric acid standard solution of the same concentration, to correct for instrument-
213 induced mass fractionation. A detailed description of analytical procedure, along with
214 accuracy of several analyses of NIST SRM 951 and other international and in-house
215 standards is available in (Agostini et al., 2021).

216 Strontium isotope analyses were performed using a Thermo Fisher Scientific Neptune
217 Plus MC-ICP-MS at IGG-CNR of Pisa as described in detail in [Agostini et al. \(2022\)](#).
218 After sample powder digestion in concentrated HF+HNO₃, strontium was extracted
219 from matrix in a class 100 clean room by ion-exchange purification through Sr-spec
220 resin Strontium analyses were performed in 2% HNO₃ solution containing 100-200
221 ng*g⁻¹ of analyte. Values are corrected for ⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr of NBS 987 =0.710248.

222 Whole-rock analyses were performed at the Service d'Analyse des Roches et
223 Minéraux (SARM, Centre de Recherches Pétrographiques et Géochimiques, Nancy,
224 France) by alkali fusion of rock samples (LiBO₂), followed by concentration
225 measurements using an ICP-OES iCAP 6500 (Thermoscientific) for major elements,
226 and an ICP-MS X7 (Thermoscientific) for minor elements (protocol by Carignan et al.,
227 2001). See Supplementary Materials 1 for details on uncertainties and detection limits.

228 Numerical modeling of isotopic fractionation was done with Rayleigh and batch
229 equations and fractionation factors from Bottinga (1969) using Python.
230 Thermodynamic modeling of COH fluid and associated carbon solid was done using
231 equations from Huizenga (2005) to track the carbon activity using a python code. Both
232 models were coupled to investigate and model the interaction of the various COH
233 fluids.

234 4 Results

235 4.1 Field relationships

236 Figure 2 and Table 1 show the location and main features of the selected samples.
237 Besides samples of variably serpentinized peridotites, rodingites, and surrounding
238 metasedimentary rocks, the most important samples presented in this study were
239 collected from two main outcrops, graphite zone A and B hereafter, showing evidence
240 of graphite precipitation. Graphite zone A consists of a vertical, ~6 m thick graphite-rich
241 shear zone cutting through the ultramafic body (Fig. 2A). This is the locality first
242 described in Kerper et al. (2008). Graphite zone A is separated from the enclosing
243 serpentinized peridotite by a rather sharp boundary (Fig. 2B). However, the host
244 serpentinite next to the graphite zone selvages appears variably carbonated. The
245 carbonation is present as veins, mainly on the East side of the graphite zone, and
246 micro-scale pervasive carbonation is visible on both sides of the graphite zone (Fig.
247 2C). The second outcrop, referred to as graphite zone B is located along the contact
248 between the BMC serpentinized peridotites and amphibolites (Fig. 2D). The outcrop
249 forms a vertical wall making the boundary with the adjacent amphibolite. The
250 amphibolite next to the contact shows evidence of fluid circulation and metasomatism,
251 as indicated by the presence of cross-cutting veins (mainly albite, carbonate, and
252 graphite; Fig. 2E) and local rodingitization (mainly tremolite, garnet, epidote,
253 carbonate; Fig. 2F).

254 Samples V18-1a,c,e correspond to metasedimentary rock of the carbonaceous
255 Ottauquechee Formation, from an outcrop located in Hyde Park, Vermont 20 km south
256 of the BMC. Sample V18-1a consists of fine-grained muscovite, quartz, chlorite,
257 abundant organic matter, and other opaque minerals. Sample V18-1c is quartz-richer,
258 and contains muscovite, chlorite, minor organic matter, coarse-grained isolated and

259 locally disseminated carbonate, coarse-grained sulfides, and detrital zircons. Samples
260 V18-2a,b, V18-3a,b and V18-11 (Fig. 3) consist of slightly serpentinized peridotites.
261 Samples V18-5(a-i), V18-7a,c, and V18-Y(1,b) are from graphite zone A. Samples
262 V18-6a,d, V18-8, V18-9, and V18-10 are variably carbonated serpentinites from the
263 selvage of graphite zone A. Samples V18-12 to V18-15 are from graphite zone B and
264 correspond to variably metasomatized amphibolites and cross-cutting veins. Sample
265 V18-4 is a graphite-carbonate-bearing rodingite.

266 4.2 Petrographic features

267 Although the petrologic features of the BMC serpentinized peridotites and related
268 mafic rocks have been treated in the literature (Boutier et al., 2021; Labotka and Albee,
269 1979; Laird et al., 2001), the associated graphite mineralization remains poorly
270 investigated (Carlsen et al., 2015; Chidester et al., 1978; Kerper et al., 2008; Van
271 Baalen et al., 2009). Kerper et al. (2008) described this graphite mineralization and
272 proposed that it was due to fluid mixing between external fluids from underlying
273 carbonaceous metasediments and internal methane-rich fluids within the serpentinite.
274 However, they could not assess the origin of the methane-rich fluids. Here, the main
275 features of graphite zones A and B are presented. Details on samples V18-2a,b, V18-
276 3 and V18-4 (rodingites) can be found in Boutier et al. (2021). The sample series V18-
277 5a to 5i corresponds to a high-resolution transect across graphite zone A (Fig. 4). The
278 outcrop comprises two main lithologies, namely tremolite-chlorite-graphite-rich rocks
279 located at the center of the zone (samples V18-5c,d), and antigorite-graphite-rich
280 rocks located at the selvages (samples V18-5a,b,e,f,g,h,i). Carbonate is present at the
281 edge of the graphite zone as discordant veins (sample V18-5a), or in the matrix of both
282 antigorite-graphite rocks (V18-5i, Fig. 5A). Samples V18-7a,c display graphite
283 associated to carbonate. Samples V18-6(a,d), V18-8, V18-9, and V18-10 have

284 disseminated carbonate-veins and do not contain graphite. Samples V18-Y1 and V18-
285 Yb are two loose blocks collected at the base of the graphite zone showing
286 complementary features, possibly reflecting the early stages of fluid/rock interaction.

287 V18-5c and V18-5d correspond to samples at the center of graphite zone A. They
288 consist of tremolite (up to 200 μ m long), antigorite, chlorite, and graphite, and show
289 complex deformation features (Fig. 5B). Graphite is present in the matrix forming
290 coronas around tremolite crystals. Microstructural relationships indicate that at least
291 some of the antigorite present in these samples formed at the expense of former
292 tremolite (Fig. 5B).

293 Sample V18-5a is composed of antigorite and graphite with discordant carbonate
294 veins (Fig. 5C). However, the former presence of tremolite is clearly indicated by the
295 pseudomorphic growth of antigorite aggregates on euhedral amphibole crystals (Fig.
296 5C). By comparison with samples V18-5c,d, the microstructures suggest that the
297 graphite rims surrounding these pseudomorphoses formed prior to the replacement of
298 tremolite by antigorite. The graphite deposit coincides with the deformation
299 experienced along the graphite zone A. Similar pseudomorphic microstructure and
300 deformation can be observed in other antigorite samples from V18-5e-i.

301 Sample V18-7c corresponds to a metasomatized serpentinite to the East of graphite
302 zone A, and consists of antigorite, dolomite, calcite, brucite, and graphite. SEM-based
303 BSE imaging suggests at least local conversion of dolomite into calcite, brucite, and
304 graphite (Fig. 5D). This microstructure, however, was not observed in any of the other
305 studied samples.

306 V18-Y1 has a breccia-like structure and consists of clasts of antigorite in a matrix of
307 fine-grained foliated tremolite. Post-kinematic diopside porphyroblasts partially

308 overgrew the foliated tremolite matrix and, to minor extent, the serpentine clasts (Fig.
309 5E). This sample does not contain graphite.

310 V18-Yb shares mineralogic features of V18-Y1 with clasts of antigorite or tremolite
311 aggregates in a matrix of fine-grained tremolite (Fig. 5F). Also, in this case,
312 microstructures suggest that at least a part of the antigorite present in the rock formed
313 after the former tremolite. Graphite is abundant in the rock. It is disseminated in the
314 fine-grained tremolite matrix, and forms aggregates around larger tremolite crystals or
315 antigorite aggregates in the clasts.

316 Six samples were collected from the graphite zone B (samples V18-12a,b,c, V18-
317 13a,b, V18-14 and V18-15). Samples V18-12a and V18-12c have structures and
318 mineral assemblages similar to samples V18-5c and v18-5d of graphite zone A, with
319 tremolite crystals up to ~200 μm long in a matrix of chlorite (Fig. 6A). Graphite is
320 abundant in the matrix and forms coronas around the tremolite crystals (Fig. 6A).

321 Samples V18-12c, V18-13a, V18-13b, V18-14, and V18-15 are mainly composed of
322 brown amphibole – partially to largely replaced by green amphibole –, epidote, and
323 titanite, in agreement with previous description of variably retrogressed amphibolite-
324 facies mafic rocks in the BMC (Labotka and Albee, 1979). In addition, graphite was
325 found as inclusions along the outer rim of epidote and titanite (Fig. 6B). As observed
326 in graphite zone A, field and microstructural relationships indicate that the rock
327 recorded fluid overpressure events indicated by crosscutting veins composed of albite,
328 brown mica, carbonate, and graphite (Figs. 2E and 6C). The presence of carbonate
329 along albite-hosted hydrofractures suggests that the carbonate post-dated the
330 formation of the albite veins. Microstructures also suggest that graphite formed by
331 transformation of the vein-filling carbonate rather than coprecipitating with it (Fig. 6D).

332 This is suggested by the preferential distribution of graphite along pressure-solution
333 domains (Fig. 6C,D). The presence of secondary, CH₄-rich fluid inclusions was
334 identified in carbonate minerals by MicroRaman spectroscopy.

335 Samples V18-12c, V18-13a, V18-13b, V18-14, and V18-15 are mainly composed of
336 hornblende, epidote, titanite, and albite-carbonate veins, consistent with the BMC
337 amphibolite (Labotka and Albee, 1979), but show evidence of fluid infiltration as
338 indicated by the presence of graphite and carbonate formed along grain boundaries
339 or micro-cracks. Particularly V18-15 contains large amounts of carbonate featuring
340 methane-rich fluid inclusions.

341 4.3 Fluid inclusions analysis

342 Boutier et al., (2021) described the presence of secondary fluid inclusions containing
343 CH₄, N₂, NH₃ and S-H/H₂S in olivine from sample V18-2a in the BMC ultramafic rocks.
344 These reduced fluids were interpreted to have formed through the process of high-
345 pressure serpentinization. Here we provide additional MicroRaman data on fluid
346 inclusions from several other samples from the BMC, and more precisely in olivine
347 from a another weakly serpentinized peridotite (V18-11), in vein calcite (V18-4 and
348 V18-6d), in titanite, plagioclase, and carbonate from amphibolites (V18-12c and V18-
349 14), and in quartz from nearby metasedimentary formations (V18-1b).

350 The fluid inclusion speciation as derived from MicroRaman spectra analysis is
351 presented in Figure 3. MicroRaman spectra (Supplementary Materials 2) show the
352 presence of marked CH₄ bands (2912 cm⁻¹), as well as N₂ (2327 cm⁻¹), NH₃ (3324 cm⁻¹),
353 and S-H/H₂S (2575 cm⁻¹). This water-free fluid inclusion composition was found in
354 olivine from partially serpentinized peridotites and in calcite from the graphite zone A.
355 The proportion of CH₄ is dominant in olivine-hosted inclusions and decreases in

356 carbonate-hosted inclusions. Olivine-hosted fluid inclusions contain step-daughter
357 hydrous solid phases such as lizardite and brucite, indicating that the initial fluid
358 trapped in the olivine was aqueous. In graphite zone B, calcite-hosted inclusions show
359 similar compositions, whereas plagioclase and titanite-hosted inclusions are water-
360 dominated with less abundant CH₄ and N₂.

361 In Boutier et al. (2021) we stated that antigorite and chrysotile were the only serpentine
362 polysomes present in the BMC rocks. However, complementary observations in
363 sample V18-2a reveal the presence of veins of lizardite, in particular, brownish lizardite
364 veins that had been misinterpreted as antigorite. The presence of lizardite-vein in only
365 a few samples is not associated with compositional changes in fluid inclusion,
366 Supplementary material 2 shows olivine-hosted inclusions composition for V18-11
367 similar to the composition for V18-2a presented in Boutier et al. (2021). Therefore, we
368 conclude that this feature does not substantially affect our interpretations of the
369 metamorphic origin of the CH₄-bearing fluid inclusions and their most plausible
370 formation at antigorite-facies conditions as proposed in Boutier et al. (2021). The
371 chronological relationships between antigorite and lizardite in sample V18-2a are not
372 obvious, which possibly suggests conditions close to the antigorite-lizardite transition
373 (380-400 °C, Schwartz et al., 2013).

374 4.4 Bulk rocks trace and major elements compositions

375 Major elements of the BMC ultramafic rocks show that the least serpentized samples
376 of the BMC (V18-2a,b) share MgO vs Al₂O₃ compositions with both abyssal and
377 orogenic/ophiolitic peridotites (Fumagalli and Klemme, 2015). Tremolite-rich samples
378 located at the center of the graphite zone A display a decrease of SiO₂ and MgO
379 content, and an increase of Al₂O₃ and CaO content with respect to the surrounding
380 ultramafic rocks. Samples most affected by graphite zone B (V18-12b) display a

381 decrease of Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃ and an increase of SiO and MgO in respect to the less or
382 unaffected mafic rocks (V18-12c, V18-14, V18-15). The major element composition of
383 the samples less affected by the graphite zone B are in range of the mafic rocks
384 composition presented in Spandler et al. (2003).

385 Chondrite-normalized Rare-Earth Element (REE) spider diagrams of the studied
386 samples along with major elements data are presented in Supplementary material 3.
387 Sample V18-1a has a positive REE slope, i.e., La_N > Lu_N, consistent with terrigenous
388 sedimentary rocks (Ague, 2017; Spandler et al., 2003). Samples of BMC variably
389 serpentinized peridotites (V18-2a,b, V18-3a, V18-5b,c,d,g,h,i, V18-7a, V18-8, V18-10)
390 have very low REE concentrations and patterns consistent with serpentinized
391 ultramafic rocks (Deschamps et al., 2013). Samples from graphite zone A (V18-5a-i)
392 and highly rich in graphite (V18-7c) have REE patterns similar to the variably
393 serpentinized peridotites. Samples from amphibolite and from graphite zone B show
394 patterns typical of gabbro, with the Eu positive anomaly attributed to preferential
395 incorporation in plagioclase (Philpotts and Schnetzler, 1968). REE spectra indicate
396 that the protolith of graphite zone A and B corresponds to depleted and differentiated
397 mantle, respectively.

398 4.5 Carbon content and isotopy

399 Total organic carbon (TOC) content is presented in Table 1. The complete details
400 including standard deviation are available in Supplementary material 4. Slightly
401 serpentinized peridotite and serpentinized rocks have TOC content of 0.001-0.02 wt.
402 %. These values correspond to the range of TOC contents in ultramafic rocks from
403 Northern Apennines and ODP samples (>0.1% to 0.7%) (Schwarzenbach et al., 2013).
404 The TOC content of graphite zone A rocks ranges between 1.02 and 3.90 wt. %,

405 showing a peak of TOC in samples close to the center of the shear zone (samples
406 V18-5g and V18-5f). This peak of TOC content is not correlated with the observed the
407 presence or not of tremolite within this graphite zone (see Section 4.1).

408 The TOC content of graphite zone B ranges from 0.2 to 3.69 wt.% (Table 1). These
409 values are higher relative to the TOC content (>0.1 wt%) of mid-ocean ridge crustal
410 rocks and their metamorphic equivalents (Schwarzenbach et al., 2013; Shilobreeva et
411 al., 2011).

412 The TOC contents of samples V18-1a,c,e from the Ottawaquechee formation range
413 from 0.17 wt% to 1.99 wt.% and are consistent with the range of TOC contents of black
414 schists (Peltola, 1968; Zhang et al., 2018).

415 Isotopic analyses of $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ were conducted to investigate the processes of graphite
416 deposition and its carbon sources. $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ data are presented in Table 1 and Figure 7,
417 with uncertainties corresponding to the standard deviation. Samples from the
418 Ottawaquechee formation (V18-1a-e) exhibit an average $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ value of -25.1 ‰
419 ($\pm 0.2\text{‰}$; n=3). These values are consistent with the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ signature of chlorite-biotite
420 zone metapelitic rocks unaffected by fluid-rock interactions from the Appalachian belt
421 (Cook-Kollars et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2018). The average $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ of least
422 serpentinized peridotites is -27.9 ‰ ($\pm 0.4\text{‰}$; n=5), which is consistent with the
423 signature of serpentinized peridotites of oceanic affinity (Schwarzenbach et al., 2013).
424 However, it corresponds to a relatively low amount of carbon (< 0.03 wt%) and could
425 be attributed to recent or biological contamination, as $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of C3 photosynthesis range
426 around -28 ‰. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ values of samples from graphite zone A and B are
427 comparable and correspond to -15.9 ‰ ($\pm 1\text{‰}$; n=9) and -15.2 ‰ ($\pm 1.2\text{‰}$; n=3),
428 respectively. These values are clearly different from the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ signature of regular

429 ultramafic rocks of the BMC. The value of graphite-poor serpentinite located close to
430 graphite zone A ranges from -29.5 to -20.2 ‰ (Table 1). A graphite-bearing
431 amphibolite next to graphite zone B has a $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ value of -20.5 ‰ (Table 1).

432 The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ values of serpentinites around the graphite zone A show disparity which
433 could correspond to the influence of the graphite zone A. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ of the samples
434 are not correlated to the direct proximity to the graphite zone A, as the samples directly
435 located near it, such as V18-6a ($\delta^{13}\text{C} = -28.6$ ‰), do not exhibit $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ value close to
436 the graphite zone A ($\delta^{13}\text{C} = -15.9$). However, the TOC content indicates a correlation
437 with the graphite zones (Fig. 8A), showing that samples with increasing TOC content
438 have values closer to that of the graphite zone A and B. Both samples from the
439 graphite veins in the ultramafic body and the amphibolite contact show $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ signature
440 centered around -15 ‰ and is homogeneous, indicating a common source for graphite
441 zone A and B. However, the variation of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ inside the graphite veins appears
442 uncorrelated to the TOC content of the samples (Fig. (8A), as samples with similar
443 TOC content range from -17.7 ‰ to -13.6 ‰.

444 Carbonates (inorganic carbon) present as veins, associated with serpentine, or in
445 rodingites exhibit a $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{inorg}}$ signature ranging from -6.49 to -1.27 ‰ (Table 1 and Fig.
446 7). The carbonate in altered amphibolite V18-14 has a value of -7.62 ‰. These values
447 are lower relative to the average signature of carbonate in metamorphic carbonated
448 ultramafic rocks (Collins et al., 2015), with the exception of rocks with low
449 carbonate/silicate ratios and affected by CO_2 -producing metamorphic decarbonation
450 reactions or fluid-deposited carbonates derived from infiltration of fluids sourced from
451 OC-bearing metasedimentary rocks (Bebout, 1991; Bebout and Barton, 1993;
452 Scambelluri et al., 2016). Additional interpretations are discussed in Section 5.2. The

453 oxygen isotopic composition $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of carbonate relative to the SMOW ranges from 8.91
454 to 16.64 ‰ (Fig. 9). These values are consistent with $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of carbonate in ultramafic
455 rocks metamorphosed to blueschist-facies conditions (Collins et al., 2015). However,
456 the carbonate $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values indicate disequilibrium with the associated BMC antigorite
457 serpentinites. For instance, carbonate values close to 9 ‰ are in equilibrium with
458 serpentine (at 6.4 ‰) for temperatures around 300-400 °C, however the highest value
459 (i.e. 16.64 ‰) would indicate equilibrium $T < 100$ °C (Saccocia et al., 2009; Wenner
460 and Taylor, 1971; Zheng, 1999, 1993) which is inconsistent with the antigorite-facies
461 metamorphic evolution of the BMC (Guillot et al., 2015). From Figure 9, it can be
462 observed that the variability of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of carbonate correlates with the distance
463 from the graphite zone. This correlation is discussed in Section 5.2.

464 Raman spectroscopy of carbonaceous material (RSCM) present in metasedimentary
465 sample V18-1a was conducted to estimate maximum temperature of graphite
466 crystallization according to (Lünsdorf et al., 2014). Spectra collected (n=14) indicate a
467 temperature of 435 +/- 14 °C.

468 The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ of CH_4 extracted from fluid inclusions from the studied BMC and
469 associated metasedimentary formations are available in Table 1. Fluid inclusions from
470 metasedimentary sample V18-1 display a $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of -46.3 ‰ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ of -226 ‰ for CH_4
471 and a $\delta^2\text{H}$ of -812 ‰ for H_2 (Fig. 10A). Partially serpentinized peridotite (olivine-hosted)
472 fluid inclusions from sample V18-2a show values of $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$ of -12.6 ‰ and $\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{CH}_4}$ of
473 -171 ‰ while V18-11 show values of $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$ of -45.2 ‰ and $\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{CH}_4}$ of -226 ‰.
474 Carbonate-hosted fluid inclusions from V18-4, V18-6d and V18-15 show values
475 ranging from $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$ of -15.5 ‰ and $\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{CH}_4}$ of -168 ‰ to $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$ of -31.3 ‰ and
476 $\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{CH}_4}$ of -177 ‰. Graphite-bearing titanite and plagioclase-hosted inclusions from

477 samples V18-12a,c and V18-14 shows values ranging from $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$ of -12.6 ‰ and
478 $\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{CH}_4}$ of -171 ‰ to $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$ of -12.6 ‰ and $\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{CH}_4}$ of -171 ‰. H_2 was present in
479 measurable amounts only in sample V18-12c and has a value $\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{H}_2}$ of -680 ‰ (Fig.
480 10B).

481 C1/C2 ratios are presented in Table 1 and show a low value of 13.23 for V18-1 typical
482 of thermogenic sources (Martini et al., 2008), whereas samples from the BMC show a
483 wider range of values. Olivine-hosted inclusions in sample V18-2a has a C1/C2 ratio
484 of 1992, while V18-11 have a value of 668. Carbonate-hosted fluid inclusions in V18-
485 4 have a C1/C2 ratio of 6154 and of 635 in V18-6d. The amount of C_2H_6 is below the
486 detection threshold in some samples leading to the absence of C1/C2 ratio.

487 4.6 Sr and B isotopes results

488 Strontium isotopic analyses were conducted on different BMC rock types and are
489 presented in Table 1 and Figure 8B. The $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ of the sample V18-1a from the
490 Ottawaquechee formation is 0.7578. The values of the BMC least serpentinized
491 peridotites (V18-2a,b and V18-3a) range from 0.7082 to 0.7095 and $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ of least
492 altered amphibolite (V18-14) is 0.7093. Serpentinite and samples from the graphite
493 zones have similar $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ values between 0.7107 and 0.7177. Overall, the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$
494 ratios of BMC samples is higher than Basaltic Achondrite Best Initial (BABI), and are
495 not compatible with Mid-Ocean Ridge Basalt (MORB) signature and depleted mantle
496 (DM) signature.

497 In a similar way, boron isotopes $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ were investigated to assess fluid sources in the
498 BMC. $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ values are negative (Table 1, Fig. 8B). The $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ of the Ottawaquechee
499 formation (V18-1a) is -8.5 ‰. The $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ of the BMC least serpentinized peridotites
500 (V18-2a,b and V18-3a) ranges from -1.6 to -0.8 ‰ and $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ of the least altered

501 amphibolite (18-14) is -3.49 ‰. Serpentinite samples (V18-7c and V18-10) and from
502 graphite zone A (V18-5c) have $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ values ranging from -4.6 to -2.4 ‰.

503 5 Discussion

504 5.1 Origin of the Belvidere graphite

505 The BMC graphite distribution and isotopic signatures suggest a fluid-deposited origin.
506 The graphite concentrations in the BMC up to 3.91 wt% are very high compared to the
507 average organic carbon content of subducted ultramafic and mafic rocks, usually
508 clustering at 0.1 wt % (Alt and Teagle, 1999; Collins et al., 2015; Schwarzenbach et
509 al., 2013; Shilobreeva et al., 2011). The graphite $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (-15.9 ‰, $\pm 1\text{‰}$) in Zone A and
510 (-15.3 ‰, $\pm 1.2\text{‰}$) in zone B differs from the total organic carbon signature of
511 subducted mafic and ultramafic rocks from -26.6 ‰ to -28 ‰ (Alt and Teagle, 1999;
512 Collins et al., 2015; Schwarzenbach et al., 2013; Shilobreeva et al., 2011), and from
513 mantle carbon at -10 ‰ to -4 ‰ (Deines, 1992; Javoy et al., 1986).

514 The graphite host rocks also confirm the hypothesis of fluid circulation and intense
515 metasomatism. In particular, in graphite zone A, structural and geochemical features
516 indicate that the rock was transiently enriched in Ca, Si and Al, as indicated by the
517 presence of tremolite and chlorite, as observed in sample V18-Y1 with the formation
518 of tremolite matrix sealing serpentine clasts (Fig. 5D). This stage is followed by
519 graphite precipitation, as observed in samples V18-Yb and V18-5c, with the growth of
520 tremolite crystals, the partial preservation of antigorite clasts and the precipitation of
521 graphite coronae around tremolite crystals (Fig. 5(A,E)). Finally, the tremolite was
522 statically replaced by antigorite, indicating a loss of Ca and enrichment in Mg, as
523 observed in sample V18-5a (Fig. 5B). The collected samples suggest that this stage
524 was more intense at the edges of graphite zone A. Carbonate precipitation at zone A

525 selvages may have occurred during the initial stages of fluid infiltration, or earlier.
526 Microstructural features indicate that the initial stage of fluid infiltration was
527 accompanied by fluid overpressure and brecciation, followed by intense syn-tremolite
528 shear deformation, and finally static replacement of tremolite by antigorite.

529 In graphite zone B, graphite precipitated at the interface between ultramafic and mafic
530 rocks. Also, in this case, petrography and microstructural analysis indicates that fluid
531 overpressure was locally achieved in the mafic rocks adjacent to the ultramafic rocks,
532 as indicated by brecciation of albite and precipitation of carbonate along fractures.
533 These mineralogical and structural relationships indicate that the carbonate
534 precipitation event took place at retrograde post-amphibolite greenschist-facies
535 conditions (albite stable). The carbonate stable isotope signature may be consistent
536 with an organic matter-rich metasedimentary fluid source (see also (Spandler et al.,
537 2008) for similar interpretations in New Caledonia). This interpretation would be
538 consistent with the regional setting of the BMC. The microstructural distribution of
539 graphite, and the presence of CH₄-rich fluid inclusions in the rock, may suggest a
540 possible H₂-mediated carbonate reduction as the origin of the graphite (Galvez et al.,
541 2013; Giuntoli et al., 2020; Malvoisin et al., 2012; Peng et al., 2022; Vitale Brovarone
542 et al., 2017). This is also suggested by some microstructures in graphite zone A (Fig.
543 5E) and in other metamorphic settings in the presence of subduction zone
544 serpentinization (Giuntoli et al., 2020; Vitale Brovarone et al., 2017). A prograde,
545 closed system carbonate reduction (e.g., Tao et al., 2018) appears inconsistent with
546 the retrograde timing of the graphite formation (syn-greenschist facies).

547 5.2 Source of carbon for methane formation

548 The graphite and methane isotopic composition alone does not allow identifying a
549 clear carbon source. In particular, the graphite signature of $\delta^{13}\text{C} = -17$ to -15 ‰ may
550 be compatible with either organic or inorganic sources, internal or external to the BMC.
551 For example, graphite in metasedimentary rocks from Appalachian metasedimentary
552 rocks shows $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ ranging from about -27 to -2 ‰ (Evans et al., 2002; Zhang et al.,
553 2018). Fluid-deposited graphite from New Hampshire, which is interpreted to derive
554 from mixing of metasediment-derived fluids, shows $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values ranging from -29 to $-$
555 9 ‰ (Rumble et al., 1986). The methane isotopic signature of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ from BMC
556 rocks indicates, at least in some samples, the contribution of biogenic organic matter
557 (Fig. 10A). Samples V18-11, with an isotopic composition of -45.2 ‰ for $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$ and
558 -226 ‰ for $\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{CH}_4}$ has values similar to the methane from graphite-rich
559 metasedimentary sample V18-1 (-46.3 ‰ for $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$ and -226 ‰ for $\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{CH}_4}$). In other
560 samples of partially serpentinized peridotite petrographically equivalent to V18-11,
561 sample V18-2, the methane signature is very different ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4} -12.9$ ‰; $\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{CH}_4} -171$
562 ‰), which may be consistent with processes involving various sources, including
563 organic and inorganic (i.e., carbonate) sources, internal or external to the BMC.

564 The combination of $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ and $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ data show a mixing trend between two end
565 members (Fig. 8B), with a metasedimentary pole defined by V18-1 with low $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ value
566 (-8.48 ‰) and extremely high $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ value (0.7578) and on the other end a
567 serpentinized peridotite pole defined by V18-2b and V18-3a ($\delta^{11}\text{B} = -0.83$ ‰ and -1.41
568 ‰, $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr} = 0.7095$ and 0.7082). The $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ values of the BMC ultramafic and
569 mafic rocks are either higher relative to their protolith rocks, or seawater which suggest
570 contamination by sedimentary or crustal reservoirs (Cannaò et al., 2016; Yamaoka et

571 al., 2012). The $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ values of the BMC rocks are negative, which is consistent with
572 serpentinization and metasomatism driven by the infiltration of metamorphic fluids
573 (Martin et al., 2020), rather than seafloor metamorphism, which would result in much
574 higher $\delta^{11}\text{B}$.

575 The presence of high nitrogen concentrations in the BMC fluid inclusions (enriched in
576 N_2 and NH_3 species) also suggests a metasedimentary source (Boutier et al., 2021
577 and references therein). Additionally, the presence of abundant sulfur in the BMC fluid
578 inclusions is also consistent with a metapelitic fluid source (Bebout and Fogel, 1992;
579 Evans et al., 2014; Kelemen and Manning, 2015; Plank and Manning, 2019).

580 According to the above considerations, at least a part of the carbon in the system was
581 sourced from the surrounding metasedimentary formations. However, the collected
582 data also outline an internal production of CH_4 . For example, SEM images suggests
583 carbonates of the BMC as a potential source of carbon for methane production through
584 reduction processes (Sections 4.2). The carbonate $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data in the BMC
585 ultramafic rocks may be interpreted as a reactional trend (Fig. 9). Graphite-free
586 carbonated serpentinites (V18-6a and V18-14) show low carbonate $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
587 values while carbonate from graphite-bearing ultramafic rocks (V18-7c and V18-5i)
588 shows higher $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values. Carbonate-graphite isotopic equilibrium would
589 lead to unrealistic temperatures or gradients, from 150°C to 550°C from the graphite-
590 free selvages to the center of graphite zone A based on fractionation factors from
591 Bottinga, (1968). Instead, owing to the positive carbonate-methane isotopic
592 fractionation during carbonate reduction, it is predicted to produce such a trend in the
593 remaining carbonate fraction (Fig. 9; Galvez et al., 2013; Vitale Brovarone et al., 2017).
594 Alternatively, because of the negative carbonate-carbon dioxide isotopic fractionation,

595 carbonate-silicate reactions producing carbon dioxide with increasing metamorphic
596 conditions is known to induce a decrease in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (Cook-Kollars et al., 2014; Piccoli et
597 al., 2016; Valley, 1986) and could explain the reactional trend. However, the observed
598 isotopic shift seems to correlate with the formation of graphite rather than with an
599 increase in carbonate-silicate reactions. Based on the above considerations, the lower
600 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ carbonates are interpreted as the earliest ones in the studied BMC rocks. These
601 values are low compared to marine carbonate and carbonate in ophicarbonates
602 (Collins et al., 2015). Such low initial values may have been achieved as a result of
603 prograde decarbonation reactions, or from the precipitation of an isotopically light
604 isotopic fluid source such as the above-mentioned graphite-bearing metasediment-
605 derived fluid. A similar process was described for fluid-deposited carbonates found in
606 metasomatized ultramafic rocks in New Caledonia (Spandler et al., 2008).

607 As outlined in Section 5.3, the evolution of the external metasediment-derived fluid
608 during progressive serpentinization of the ultramafic body and its mixing with methane-
609 rich reduced fluids resulting from carbonate reduction may easily overprint the original
610 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of the infiltrating fluid in favor of the newly formed methane (i.e., the methane
611 formed through carbonate reduction). Figure 10A shows the mixing trend between the
612 metasedimentary source at $\delta^{13}\text{C} = -45\text{‰}$ $\delta^2\text{H} = -240\text{‰}$ and the methane produced
613 through carbonate reduction ranging from $\delta^{13}\text{C} = -23\text{‰}$ to -12‰ and $\delta^2\text{H} = -140\text{‰}$.
614 Figure 11 shows that the model of methanation of carbonate from the BMC is
615 consistent with the isotopic value of the methane ranging outside the thermogenic
616 domain. However, such a trend could have been shifted to lower values by varying
617 mixing trends with the isotopically lighter ($\delta^{13}\text{C} = -45\text{‰}$) metasediment-derived fluid.

618 5.2.1 Fluid evolution and mechanism of graphite formation

619 Graphite precipitation may occur through multiple processes, which depend on the
620 evolution of fluids and/or their interactions with the host rock. Four different
621 mechanisms, which likely all together participated in the precipitation of graphite in the
622 BMC, are considered in the present study, namely fluid dehydration –hereafter
623 desiccation–, fluid mixing, changes in the ambient redox conditions, and carbonate
624 reduction (Connolly, 1995; Duke and Rumble, 1986; Galvez et al., 2013; Holloway,
625 1984; Luque del Villar et al., 1998; Malvoisin et al., 2012; Vitale Brovarone et al., 2017).
626 Other mechanisms, such as isobaric cooling or isothermal compression, are
627 considered less plausible and will not be discussed further.

628 In a COH system, the graphite stability field is not only favored by with increasing
629 pressure, and diminishes with increasing temperature (Cesare, 1995). Its stability is
630 also dependent on the fluid component speciation, which is in turn dependent on the
631 redox state of the system, and graphite can precipitate at fixed P-T conditions for
632 varying fluid compositions and redox conditions. The redox state of a ternary COH
633 system has been discussed as a function of the parameter X_O ($X_O = \frac{n_O}{n_O + n_H}$) (Connolly,
634 1995; Connolly and Cesare, 1993). The maximum graphite stability for low carbon
635 concentrations in a COH fluid is observed when the fluid-component speciation is
636 dominantly H₂O, the so called “water maximum” ($X_O = 1/3$). At fixed P and T, fluid
637 infiltration can lead to graphite precipitation if X_O changes during the fluid-rock
638 interaction. In a similar fashion, desiccation will lead to a change in the ratio of H₂O,
639 CO₂, and CH₄ in the fluid and to the precipitation of graphite according to the following
640 reaction: $CH_4 + CO_2 = 2C + 2H_2O$ (Duke and Rumble, 1986). Fluid interactions have
641 the potential to deposit graphite in amounts varying as a function of the intensity of the
642 X_O variations. Desiccation leads to graphite precipitation proportional to the intensity

643 of the water loss. A micro-scale example of fluid desiccation is testified by the presence
644 of olivine-hosted gaseous fluid inclusions filled with hydrous step-daughter minerals in
645 the BMC, which indicate that the water present in the original entrapped fluids was
646 progressively exhausted by hydration reactions of the inclusion walls (Boutier et al.,
647 2021; see also Klein et al., 2019). With progressive exhaustion of the H₂O component
648 and residual enrichment of carbon in the remaining fluid, the system may reach carbon
649 saturation and graphite precipitation (see also Andreani et al. (2023) for the
650 precipitation of different carbonaceous complexes). Graphite was found only locally as
651 a step-daughter mineral in the BMC fluid inclusions (Boutier et al., 2021). This
652 indicates that fluid desiccation inside the fluid inclusions cannot account for the
653 precipitation of substantial graphite amounts along shear zones and lithologic
654 boundaries as observed in the BMC. However, the desiccation process may have
655 taken place at larger scales during the progressive infiltration of metamorphic fluids
656 responsible for the partial hydration of the BMC ultramafic rocks.

657 Based on the collected data, the main fluid infiltration event can be described as an
658 H₂O-rich fluid equilibrated with a carbon-bearing metasedimentary source. Sample
659 V18-1 suggests that this fluid may have had a low $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ signature (Table 1). This initial
660 isotopic composition may be preserved in the fluid inclusions of samples V18-11 and
661 V18-14, as indicated by the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values of CH₄. A slightly reduced ($X_{\text{O}} \lesssim \frac{1}{3}$)
662 graphite-saturated COH fluid near water maximum can be dominated by CH₄ with
663 respect to CO₂. For instance, a carbon-saturated COH fluid at $X_{\text{O}}=0.33$ (QFM -0.5) at
664 450 °C and 1.1 GPa (conditions estimated for the hydration of the peridotite body and
665 consistent with the thermal metamorphic peak of the surrounding metasedimentary
666 units, Boutier et al., 2021) would consist of 98% (molar) of H₂O with a $\frac{\text{CO}_2}{\text{CH}_4+\text{CO}_2}=0.32$.
667 Such fluid would have plenty of water available to hydrate the peridotite body. This

668 hypothesis is supported by the fluid inclusion composition (Boutier et al., 2021) and
669 bulk-rock isotopic signatures discussed in the previous sections, which all together
670 suggest serpentinization by metasediment-derived fluids. Owing to the formation of
671 hydrous phases such as antigorite and chlorite and to the partial oxidation of iron to
672 form magnetite, the evolution of this externally derived fluid during serpentinization
673 would encounter two important changes, which are progressive desiccation and
674 reduction. The decreasing fO_2 during metamorphic serpentinization of the BMC may
675 have in fact enhanced the conversion of the more oxidized fraction (e.g., carbon
676 dioxide, bicarbonates) of the infiltrating fluid to additional methane. Because a carbon-
677 saturated fluid at water maximum corresponds to the minimum of carbon solubility,
678 desiccation of this fluid toward more reducing conditions would increase the fraction
679 of carbon in the fluid in favor of methane-dominated compositions. This process,
680 described by the model in Figure 12A-D, may precipitate graphite. The model
681 considers desiccation of 100 moles of metasediment-derived fluid at 450 °C and 1.1
682 GPa in a closed system. The initial redox state of the fluid was set slightly below the
683 water maximum ($X_{O_2} = 0.33$) in order to allow the model to spontaneously proceed
684 toward more reducing conditions during desiccation (Fig. 12A-C). The model predicts
685 that full desiccation of this fluid would precipitate 1.24 moles of graphite (per 100 moles
686 of initial fluid, Fig. 12D). However, this model fails at reproducing the graphite isotopic
687 compositions as measured in the BMC sample. Considering an infiltrating fluid with
688 $\delta^{13}C = -45\text{‰}$ (as measured in samples V18-1A and V18-11), desiccation would lead
689 to the precipitation of graphite with a too low $\delta^{13}C$ signature (Fig. 12E). A plausible
690 way to obtain relative heavier $\delta^{13}C$ value is the participation of carbonate present in
691 the BMC mafic and ultramafic rocks. The BMC rocks present evidence of carbonate
692 reduction, as illustrated by SEM imaging (V18-7c) (Fig. 5D), suggesting reduction of

693 dolomite into calcite and brucite along with the release of CH₄ and H₂O (Peng et al.,
694 2021), and formation of graphite around dolomite relicts. The reduction of carbonate
695 in the ultramafic body, favored by decreasing fO_2 in the evolved infiltrating fluid, could
696 additionally increase the methane concentration in the fluid and impose a heavier
697 isotopic composition to the fluid. Isotopically labeled dissolution experiments of
698 carbonate-graphite mixtures have shown that the isotopic composition of graphite-
699 derived CO₂ can be buffered by the isotopic composition of carbonate, regardless of
700 the carbonate/graphite ratios (Tumiati et al., 2022). Those experiments did not
701 consider reducing conditions. However, considering that the reduction of carbonate
702 releases more carbon than carbonate dissolution in pure water (Lazar et al., 2012),
703 and that the initial infiltrating fluid likely was water-rich and carbon-poor (near the water
704 maximum), it can be expected that the carbon isotopic composition of the precipitated
705 graphite was controlled more by the carbonate than the desiccated infiltrating fluid.
706 Moreover, the infiltrating fluid was initially water-dominated, and its desiccation would
707 produce a much smaller amounts of carbon-rich fluid, favoring carbonate as a carbon
708 isotopic buffer. In this case, the transformation of methane at $\delta^{13}C = -23\text{‰}$ produced
709 from the reduction of the least altered carbonate in the BMC ultramafic rocks would
710 lead to the precipitation of graphite with $\delta^{13}C = -15\text{‰}$ to -16.5‰ at 400-450°C. This
711 calculated $\delta^{13}C$ range fits well the range of $\delta^{13}C$ values measured for the BMC graphite
712 and could explain its precipitation mechanism through coupled desiccation and
713 carbonate reduction. Furthermore, the participation of carbonate in the graphite
714 precipitation mechanism may explain the mineralogical variations within graphite zone
715 A, with replacement of antigorite by tremolite.

716 The distribution of graphite in the BMC along shear zones and lithologic boundaries
717 suggests that these structures acted as major fluid channels. Although the mechanism

718 of graphite precipitation presented above may explain the measured graphite $\delta^{13}\text{C}$
719 values, it represents a static, or instantaneous process, with one single fluid influx from
720 the surrounding metasedimentary rocks. Because a more realistic, dynamic process
721 may imply continuous or multiple fluid influx from the surrounding metasedimentary
722 units and the migration of the evolved fluids outside the BMC, we also consider a
723 graphite precipitation model involving mixing between the metasediment-derived fluid
724 and its evolved (desiccation + carbonate reduction) equivalent.

725 In this model, presented in Figure 12F-J, the mixing of an external metasedimentary
726 fluid with a $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of methane at -45‰ (sample V18-1) and a methane-rich fluid around
727 $\delta^{13}\text{C} = -23\text{‰}$ (samples V18-2 and V18-4) formed inside the BMC, would lead to the
728 precipitation of graphite at $\delta^{13}\text{C} = -14\text{‰}$ to -18‰ at 450°C and 1.1 GPa (pressure
729 constrained by Honsberger, 2015; Laird et al., 1993 for the BMC) (Fig. 12J). The
730 amount of graphite precipitated through this mechanism is estimated to be 1.39 mol
731 for 200 mol of fluid and corresponds to 5% of the carbon in the initial fluid (Fig. 12).

732 This model shows that the observed carbon isotope values of graphite, carbonate, and
733 methane can be explained through the infiltration of a single low $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ fluid, its evolution
734 during serpentinization inside the BMC, and their remixing along major fluid channels.
735 The escape of the strongly reduced fluid formed in response to serpentinization may
736 have encountered redox variations while reaching the surrounding rocks. This may
737 also participate in the formation of graphite-rich rocks in graphite zone B. The BMC
738 would act as an open system with infiltration localized along fluid channels with initial
739 intake of metasedimentary equilibrated water and outtake of serpentinization-related
740 reduced fluid.

741 The above models are also supported the silicate fraction of the graphite-rich rocks.
742 Samples from graphite zone A show an initial Ca enrichment and Sr isotopic signature
743 consistent with metasediment-derived fluids, followed by a Ca depletion and Mg
744 enrichment, which may be consistent with a reinjection of evolved, serpentinization-
745 related fluids inside a preferential fluid pathway such as graphite zones A and B. The
746 petrological features observed at the edge of the graphite zone A are consistent with
747 the escape of an internal Mg-rich fluid leading to the retromorphism of tremolite
748 crystals to antigorite (V18-5a)(Fig. 5B).

749 In summary, the precipitation of graphite in the BMC can be summarized in four majors
750 steps, as follows, and is illustrated in an idealized sketch in Figure 13:

751 1- The BMC was infiltrated by metasediment-derived fluids, resulting in metasomatism
752 (e.g, Ca enrichment; negative $\delta^{11}\text{B}$; high $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$) along major fluid channels (e.g.
753 graphite zones A and B).

754 2- This fluid progressively equilibrated with the BMC ultramafic rocks during pervasive
755 serpentinization in the antigorite stability field and may be responsible for the
756 precipitation of isotopically light carbonate in the BMC rocks.

757 3- The metamorphic serpentinization of the BMC led to progressive desiccation of the
758 infiltrating fluid and decreasing $f\text{O}_2$ conditions, which promoted additional methane
759 formation through carbonate reduction and/or respeciation of more oxidized fluids.
760 These processes may have participated in the precipitation of graphite.

761 4- The CH_4 -enriched fluids resulting from the BMC serpentinization and carbonate
762 reduction were reinjected along fluid channels, causing additional metasomatism (Mg

763 enrichment and Ca depletion) and favoring fluid mixing and additional graphite
764 precipitation.

765

766 5.3 Consideration on the origin of metamorphic methane in the BMC

767 The BMC methane is an example of an increasing number of reports of methane in
768 subduction zone metamorphic rocks. Abiotic methanogenesis in ultramafic rocks has
769 been shown at natural conditions spanning seafloor hydrothermalism, magmatism,
770 and on-land surficial serpentinization (e.g., Etiope and Sherwood Lollar, 2013). This is
771 an important process in deep subsurface biosphere research and geoastronomy, as
772 it is considered as a source of prebiotic organic compounds and their possible role on
773 the origin of life on Earth and potentially elsewhere (Colman et al., 2017; Holm et al.,
774 2015; Schulte et al., 2006).

775 The initial infiltrating fluid of the proposed evolution may have contained CH₄. If this
776 fluid equilibrates at water maximum, graphite-saturated conditions, a roughly
777 comparable concentration of CH₄ and CO₂ is expected. Sample V18-1 from the
778 Ottawaquechee metasedimentary formation contains CH₄ in fluid inclusions. This CH₄
779 can be interpreted as methane formed as a result of graphite-saturated COH
780 thermodynamics, as conventionally proposed for metapelitic rocks, which would be by
781 definition abiotic. However, the analyzed $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ data of CH₄ from this sample
782 indicate a thermogenic origin, which is classically considered as biotic. Thermogenic
783 production of CH₄ is generally believed to be limited to about 300 °C (Mangenot et al.,
784 2018; Stolper et al., 2015, 2014). The Ottawaquechee metasediments experienced
785 metamorphism to about 434 °C, as indicated by RSCM thermometry. This temperature

786 is well above the conventional limit of thermogenic methane. The interaction of this
787 fluid with the BMC promoted serpentinization and additional reduction of the fluid.
788 During this event, the CO₂ present in the infiltrating fluid (for reference, a graphite
789 saturated fluid at 400 °C, 1.0 GPa, and X_o = 0.333 contains a CH₄/CO₂ ratio of 1) is
790 expected to be converted into CH₄ through a process of CO₂ reduction that is, by
791 definition, abiotic. However, its signature would still appear biotic.

792 The reduction of carbonates by the serpentinization-related reducing fluids promoted
793 additional formation of methane. This methane must be considered abiotic in origin
794 and, depending on the degree of mixing with the external fluid, may still record its
795 inorganic source. However, in the case of the BMC, the isotopic signature of the
796 reactant carbonates was negative (-7.26 to -1.43 ‰) and was potentially affected by
797 previous interaction with fluids recording an organic carbon source.

798 Grozeva et al., 2020 report δ¹³C isotopic values for abiotic methane in inclusions from
799 two active serpentinization systems ranging from -16.7 ‰ to -4.4 ‰ in the Von Damm
800 hydrothermal field and ranging from -12.4 ‰ to -2.8 ‰ for the Zambales ophiolite. In
801 both datasets C1/C2 values range from 163 to 1372 and cluster around 400. The main
802 mechanism proposed for methane formation is the conversion of mantle CO₂ to CH₄
803 and the carbon isotopic composition of the CH₄ reflects the isotopic composition of
804 mantle CO₂ along with variations caused by the carbon isotopic composition in the
805 host rock. Data from Grozeva et al. 2020 are akin to values of V18-2 and V18-4 fluid
806 inclusions reflecting the abiotic hydrocarbon production of the BMC. However, the fluid
807 composition of the BMC (rich in C, N, and S) strongly differs from the inclusions
808 analyzed by Grozeva et al. 2020, and the collected data point to a different,
809 metamorphic origin in the Taconic subduction zone.

810 The distribution of more biotic or abiotic signatures across the BMC depict the
811 complexity of the process of fluid infiltration and fluid-rock interactions that affected the
812 massif. Also, the collected data stress the complexity of methane generation and
813 evolution in metamorphic settings and call for additional analyses on these
814 metamorphic gases. In particular methane clumped isotope analysis has proven to
815 provide additional insight on the discrimination between biotic and abiotic processes
816 (Ono et al., 2021; Shuai et al., 2018; Young et al., 2017).

817 In conclusion, the results obtained in this work indicate that the origin and chemistry
818 of metamorphic methane can be more complex than previously assumed.

819 5.4 Implication on large scale methane production

820 Subducted fresh ultramafic bodies can act as massive converter factories of CO₂ into
821 CH₄ and other reduced carbon phases such as graphite. Because these fluids
822 circulate in the subduction channel, they can have a significant impact on the redox
823 budgets in the subduction zone. Redox barriers, that is an interface between two
824 compartments with a steep difference in redox conditions, imposed at lithological
825 contacts for example, can act as carbon sinks, such as graphite deposition, effectively
826 halting a percentage of the C transfer in metamorphic fluids.

827 When considering next the serpentizing mantle wedge, which could similarly act as
828 a powerhouse of H₂ and CH₄ formation, the path taken by the resultant fluids will
829 impact significantly on the formation or precipitation of these compounds. This can in
830 turn hamper the quantification of the methane release from subduction zones, as many
831 redox barriers – including the activity of microorganisms within the biosphere – can be
832 expected within the mantle wedge and above inside the crust.

833 6 Conclusions

834 Petrological, Raman, and isotopic data provided additional insights on the fate of
835 carbon at the Belvidere Mountain Complex, Appalachian belt, Northern Vermont. The
836 exceptional graphite deposit observed across the study site highlights limitations on
837 carbon mobility in the subduction zone and the complex mechanism of fluid interaction
838 with evolving redox conditions. The carbon, strontium, and boron isotopes indicate
839 fluid infiltrations evolving from metasedimentary rocks in subduction zones as the
840 initial fluid influx responsible for the high-pressure serpentinization and the first
841 metasomatic event. This is consistent with the model proposed by Kerper et al. (2008).
842 Isotopic investigation of methane in fluid inclusions highlights a complex evolution
843 involving both metasediment-derived, high-temperature thermogenic (biotic) and
844 serpentinization-related (abiotic) CH₄-forming processes. Collected data and
845 numerical results point toward graphite precipitation as the results of the mixing of CH₄
846 released by the HP serpentinization of the BMC with more oxidized infiltrating fluid
847 (possibly the same fluid driving the serpentinization). This study outlines that ultramafic
848 bodies in subduction can retain their potential to be abiotic producers of methane
849 during relatively shallow subduction conditions (before antigorite destabilization).
850 However, the redox state of surrounding formations seems to play an important role
851 as it could severely impede fluid mobility of carbon. In this scope, the mantle wedge
852 interacting with the slab as a source of water and carbon could host similar reactions,
853 with implications for the redox state of subduction, carbon cycling in subduction and
854 for the interpretation of biotic vs. abiotic signatures on earth and potentially beyond. A
855 recent study highlights such a phenomenon with the high oxidation potential of the
856 metasedimentary cover of the slab demonstrating capability to convert a high amount
857 of fluid (Ague et al., 2022).

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867

8 Appendix A. Supplementary materials

Supplementary material 1 is a table providing uncertainties and detection limits for whole-rock analyses.

Supplementary material 2 includes microRaman spectroscopy results of fluids inclusions in calcite, quartz, olivine, plagioclase, and titanite. The presence of CH₄, H₂, N₂, and H₂S is shown.

Supplementary material 3 contains bulk-rock major and REE compositions of the studied rock samples. The patterns suggest that graphite zones A and B formed at the expense of ultramafic rocks.

Supplementary material 4 presents the complete carbon, oxygen, and hydrogen isotopic data from solid and fluid phases and the related uncertainties from different acquisition methods (Picarro and GC-MS).

880

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1208 Figures captions

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1210 **Fig. 1:** A: Simplified geological map of Northeast Vermont, modified from Hibbard et
1211 al., (2006). B: Simplified bedrock geologic map of the Belvidere Mountain Complex
1212 and the surrounding formations. Modified after Hibbard et al., (2006). Unit
1213 descriptions from Hibbard et al. (2006) and Gale (2007).

1214 **Fig. 2:** A-B: Field occurrence of graphite zone A (A). The graphite-enriched shear
1215 zone (B) is present inside serpentized peridotites. C: Carbonate and magnetite
1216 veins located on the sides of graphite zone A. D: Graphite zone B. The wall shown in
1217 the picture is a graphite-enriched slip plane marking the boundary between
1218 amphibolites and serpentized peridotites. The graphite enrichment can be
1219 observed within about 3 meters inside the amphibolite. E: Albite-carbonate veins
1220 cutting across the outer margin of the amphibolite next to graphite zone B. The host
1221 amphibolite is here intensely affected by greenschist-facies overprinting. F: Example
1222 of rodingite-like metasomatism locally affecting the outer portion of the amphibolite at
1223 graphite zone B. Gt: garnet; Ep: epidote; Cc: calcite.

1224 **Fig. 3:** Map showing the geology, sample location, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰ VPDB), of organic
1225 carbon content (wt. %), and $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio results. Pie charts indicate the relative
1226 composition of different phases in fluid inclusion as determined from Micro-Raman
1227 spectra following the method by Frezzotti et al. (2012). The initial presence of water
1228 in olivine-hosted fluid inclusions is deduced from the presence of hydrated step
1229 daughter minerals. See Fig. 4 for details on graphite zone A.

1230 **Fig. 4:** Field view details of graphite zone A. The location of the studied samples and
1231 associated values of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ ‰ (VPDB), wt. % of organic carbon and $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios are
1232 also shown. The black-colored area represents the location of the graphite-rich shear
1233 zone. The shaded yellow-colored area indicates the carbonate-enriched selvages next
1234 to the graphite zone. Thin section scans are also shown in order to highlight the
1235 distribution of graphite (dark samples) with respect to the enclosing graphite-free
1236 ultramafic rocks.

1237 **Fig. 5:** Photomicrographs of graphite zone A. A: Sample V18-5i from graphite zone
1238 A. Pervasive carbonate veins are crosscutting the host antigorite + graphite rock. B:
1239 Samples V18-5c from graphite zone A. Fine-grained tremolite is replaced by larger
1240 tremolite crystals. The tremolite-rich rock has been partially replaced by antigorite.
1241 Graphite appears inside antigorite clast and at the rim of tremolite crystals. C:
1242 Sample at the edge of graphite zone A (V18-5a). Tremolite crystals have been
1243 replaced by antigorite, with graphite rims outlining the pseudomorphic texture. D:
1244 SEM backscattered electron image of sample V18-7c. Carbonate reduction is
1245 suggested by the transformation of dolomite to calcite + brucite + graphite. E: Clasts
1246 of antigorite in a foliated matrix of fine grained tremolite from graphite zone A (V18-
1247 Y1). The tremolite foliation is overgrown by static diopside porphyroblasts. F: Edge of
1248 an antigorite-rich clast in contact with tremolite matrix (V18-Yb). In this case, the
1249 presence of graphite along the edges to tremolite crystals suggest that the graphite
1250 precipitation occurred after the serpentinite brecciation and tremolite precipitation in
1251 vein (cf. E). with graphite deposit associated with graphite zone A. Atg: antigorite,

1252 Trm: tremolite, Di: diopside, G: graphite, Chl: chlorite, Cc: calcite, Dol, dolomite, Br:
1253 brucite.

1254 **Fig. 6:** Photomicrographs of graphite zone B. A: Tremolite-graphite assemblage
1255 (V18-12a), analogous to samples observed in graphite zone A. B: Graphite rimming
1256 epidote and titanite crystals inside the edge of the amphibolite at graphite zone B
1257 (V18-12c). C-D: Brittle deformation inside albite-carbonate veins (V18-14). Note that
1258 clasts of albite crystals are sealed by carbonate. Graphite preferentially forms along
1259 pressure-solution domains at albite-carbonate boundaries (D; SEM backscattered
1260 electron image). Graphite is associated with carbonate. G: graphite, Trm: tremolite,
1261 Amph: amphibole, Ttn: titanite, Bt: biotite, Ab: albite, Cc: calcite.

1262 **Fig. 7:** A: Isotopic compositions of the main carbon bearing objects in the BMC.
1263 Error bars do not appear when comprised within the symbol size.

1264 **Fig. 8:** A: Inverse of organic carbon concentration versus $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ composition of
1265 BMC samples. B: $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ value versus $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio with data. Boron data from Martin
1266 et al., (2020) and strontium data from Cannà et al., (2016) (Cima di Gagnone) and
1267 Yamaoka et al., (2012) (Oman ophiolite). Metasediment (V18-1a) age corrected at
1268 300 Ma. DM: depleted Mantle.

1269 **Fig. 9:** Carbonate $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ isotopic compositions from the BMC. Indicative
1270 proximities to the graphite zones indicated below samples' name. Reactional trend
1271 associated with formation of CO_2 from prograde decarbonation (blue), and carbonate
1272 reduction (green) from Piccoli et al. (2018) and Debret et al. (2015).

1273 **Fig. 10:** A: Ranges of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ measured in methane-rich fluid inclusions. A
1274 variety of sources are displayed as references from Bradley and Summons (2010).
1275 'Autotrophic' refers to methane produced by H_2/CO_2 methanogenesis, while
1276 'heterotrophic' refers to methane produced by fermentation of acetate or
1277 consumption of methylated organic compounds. 'Thermogenic' refers to cracking of
1278 biologically derived oils, while 'geothermal' refers to cracking of high-molecular-
1279 weight organic compounds. B: $\delta^2\text{H}$ values of CH_4 and H_2 from fluid inclusions.
1280 Methane and hydrogen produced by activity of methanogens are expected to fall
1281 within the grey box and additional reference data from Bradley and Summons,
1282 (2010).

1283 **Fig. 11:** Modeling of equilibrium fractionation for methanation of calcite at 450 °C. A
1284 calcite with an initial $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ isotopic composition of -8 ‰ is considered, using
1285 fractionation factor from Bottinga (1969).

1286 **Fig. 12:** Modeling at 450°C and 1.1 GPa of the desiccation of a fluid near water
1287 maximum toward reducing conditions fluid with an isotopic composition of $\delta^{13}\text{C}=-45$
1288 ‰ (A-E), and modeling of the mixing of a slightly reduced fluid with an isotopic
1289 composition of $\delta^{13}\text{C}=-45$ ‰ and a reduced fluid with an isotopic composition of
1290 $\delta^{13}\text{C}=-23$ ‰ (F-J). A and F: zoom on a COH diagram of the initial and final position
1291 of the involved fluids. B and G: evolution of the $\text{CH}_4/(\text{CH}_4+\text{CO}_2)$ ratio and of the
1292 $\text{H}_2\text{O}/(\text{CH}_4+\text{CO}_2+\text{H}_2\text{O})$ ratio during the modeled fluid interactions. C and H: evolution
1293 of the oxygen fugacity of the fluid during the modeled fluid interactions. D and I:

1294 *evolution of the total amount of graphite in mole in the system during the modeled*
1295 *fluid interactions. E and J: evolution of the isotopic composition of the main carbon*
1296 *bearing species in the system during the modeled fluid interaction. The model does a*
1297 *titration of one fluid in another and tracks the carbon activity of the system according*
1298 *to equation form Huizenga (2004). New graphite composition corresponds to the*
1299 *instantaneous composition of graphite precipitating while total graphite account for*
1300 *the global composition of graphite in the system.*

1301 **Fig. 13:** *Proposed model of BMC hydration in subduction zone associated with*
1302 *graphite deposition linked to CH₄ migration. A: Initial sage of the BMC in subduction,*
1303 *graphite zone A corresponds to a shear zone and graphite zone B to the lithologic*
1304 *contact with the amphibolite. B: Infiltration of a fluid from metasedimentary rocks.*
1305 *This fluid was H₂O dominated, rich in Ca, Si, C, and N, and produced tremolite*
1306 *metasomatism along the main fluid channels. C: CH₄ released from serpentinization*
1307 *escapes along main fluid channel and precipitates graphite when encountering redox*
1308 *barrier. D: As the CH₄ production and escape progresses, the CH₄ becomes*
1309 *dominant across the study zone and the redox front progresses in the amphibolite.*

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1311 Table captions

1312 **Table 1:** Studied BMC samples and related carbon, strontium and boron data.

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Table 1: Studied BMC samples and related carbon, strontium and boron data.

Samples		C_{org}	$\delta^{13}C_{org}$	$\delta^{13}C_{inorg}$	$\delta^{18}O_{carbonate}$	$\delta^{13}C_{CH_4}$
		(wt%)	VPDP	VPDP	VSMOW	VPDP picarro
V18-1a		0.58	-25.3			-46.28
V18-1c	metasedimentary rocks	0.17	-25			
V18-1e		1.99	-25			
V18-2a		0.02	-27.4			-12.66
V18-2b	mostly preserved peridotite	0.03	-28.3			
V18-3a		0.03	-28.1			
V18-3b		0.03	-28.5			
V18-4	rodingites	0.01	-21.7			-15.48
V18-Y1						
V18-Yb						
V18-5a		1.39	-15.5			
V18-5b		1.65	-15.2			
V18-5c		1.51	-15.6			
V18-5d	graphite zone A	1.08	-14.6			
V18-5e		1.03	-17			
V18-5f		3.91	-15.3			
V18-5g		2.76	-15.6			
V18-5h		1.45	-16.5			
V18-5i		1.02	-17.7	-1.43	16.64	
V18-6a		0.06	-28.6	-6.49	8.91	
V18-6d		0.03	-29.5			-31.25
V18-7a		0.07	-24.7			
V18-7c	serpentinite with variable amount of carbonate	0.09	-20.2	-1.27	15.15	
V18-8		0.02	-27.7	-4.5	10.83	
V18-9		0.02	-27.9	-4.13	11.81	
V18-10		0.37	-25.1			
V18-11	mostly preserved peridotite	0.02	-27.7			-45.23
V18-12a		3.69	-15.5			-22.36
V18-12b	graphite zone B	0.96	-13.6			
V18-12c		0.22	-16.9			-18.59
V18-13		0.77	-14.8			
V18-14	amphibolite	0.14	-20.5	-7.26	11.41	-36.95
V18-15	amphibolite with carbonate	0.43	-15.4			-20.19

$\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$	$\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{CH}_4}$	$\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{H}_2}$	C1/C2	$^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$	$\delta^{11}\text{B}$
VPDP	VSMOW	VSMOW			
IRMS					
-46.34	-226	-812	13	0.75779	-8.5
-12.93	-171		1992	0.70954	-1.6
				0.7095	-0.8
				0.70822	-1.4
-17.88	-177		6154		
				0.71495	
				0.7167	-3.6
				0.71767	
				0.71401	
-29			635		
				0.71381	-2.4
				0.71381	-4.6
-42.48	-226		668		
-22.46	-161				
-20.66	-140	-680			
-33.45	-168			0.70934	-3.5
-20.18	-168			0.7107	

 $\delta^{18}\text{O} \text{ ‰ (VSMOW)}$

Fractionation of Calcite to CH₄

